

Supplementary information

For the Journal Paper

Measurement of insertion loss and gain in variable hear-through and noise cancellation modes of true wireless earbuds

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Introduction

This supplementary information document presents additional data relevant to all sections of the journal paper “Measurement of insertion loss and gain in variable hear-through and noise cancellation modes of true wireless earbuds”. Appendix A provides the results of a properties analysis of the passive, total, and active spectral modification results presented in Figs. 2-4 of the paper. These results may be useful to researchers who wish to produce models that replicate typical insertion loss and gain performance of true wireless earbuds. Appendix B comprises of spectrograms showing various temporal discontinuities observed in the spectral modification performance of devices A and B at 105 dB SPL. Appendix C consists of spectrograms showing the onset of spectral modification for all devices.

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Appendix A

Spectral modification properties analysis

The following terminology, illustrated in Figs. A.1 and A.2, was used to describe and analyse properties of the total and active spectral modification results in this study:

- Attenuation amount - the maximum attenuation in dB provided by the device mode.
- Attenuation frequency - the central frequency in Hz (third-octave) at which the attenuation was largest for the given mode.
- Attenuation region - the breadth of the attenuation surrounding the central attenuation frequency in Hz, calculated as the span across which the attenuation was less than -3 dB. When the attenuation is indicative of a shelf rather than a band-stop the region is given as the frequency at which the attenuation first exceeds -3 dB.
- Modification range - the difference in dB between the attenuation and boosting amounts for the device mode.
- Boosting amount (Peak) - the maximum boosting in dB provided by the device mode when boosting is ≥ 0 dB; in cases where there is no boosting in a mode (Peak) this term is used to describe the amount of attenuation in the band with the lowest insertion loss.
- Boosting frequency - the central frequency in Hz (third-octave) at which the boosting was largest for the given mode.
- Boosting region - the breadth of the boosting surrounding the central boosting frequency in Hz, calculated as the span across which the boosting exceeds 3 dB. When the boosting is indicative of a shelf rather than a band-pass the region is given as the frequency at which the attenuation first exceeds 3 dB.

This same terminology is also used to analyse the passive spectral modulation results, with the exception of the term 'resonant peak' being used in place of 'boosting' where applicable.

FIGURE A.1: Diagram illustrating the spectral modification properties analysis terminology. The line plotted on this graph is not representative of any real data.

FIGURE A.2: Diagram illustrating the spectral modification attenuation and boosting region properties in cases where the modification is indicative of a shelf rather than a band.

TABLE A.1: Passive spectral modification properties analysis of results shown in Fig. 2 of the paper.

Device	Mode	Attenuation			Modification Range (dB)	Resonant Peak		
		Amount (dB)	Freq. (Hz)	Region (Hz)		Amount (dB)	Freq. (Hz)	Region (Hz)
A	<i>Off</i>	-33.57	16000	≥ 630	37.30	3.73	200	200*
B	<i>Off</i>	-33.03	20000	≥ 800	36.22	3.19	200	200*
C	<i>Off</i>	-34.13	8000	≥ 400	40.39	6.27	200	200*

*This region only occupied a single third octave band.

TABLE A.2: Total spectral modification properties analysis of results shown in Fig. 3 of the paper.

Device	Mode	Attenuation			Modification Range (dB)	Boosting (Peak)		
		Amount (dB)	Freq. (Hz)	Region (Hz)		Amount (dB)	Freq. (Hz)	Region (Hz)
A					45.81			
	<i>HTM 1</i>	-19.91	16000	≥ 5000	34.26	14.37	2500	2000-4000
	<i>HTM 2</i>	-20.11	16000	≥ 5000	33.30	13.19	2500	2000-4000
	<i>HTM 3</i>	-21.25	16000	≥ 5000	33.26	12.01	2500	2000-4000
	<i>HTM 4</i>	-22.34	16000	≥ 5000	33.21	10.88	2500	2000-3150
	<i>HTM 5</i>	-23.46	16000	≥ 5000	33.16	9.70	2500	2000-3150
	<i>HTM 6</i>	-24.53	16000	≥ 5000	33.07	8.54	2500	2000-3150
	<i>NCM</i>	-31.46	160	≥ 63	22.80	-8.65 (Peak)	3150	No boosting
B					48.67			
	<i>HTM 1</i>	-28.24	20000	≥ 5000	42.01	13.77	2000	1250-3150
	<i>HTM 2</i>	-29.78	20000	≥ 4000	40.77	10.98	2000	1600-2500
	<i>HTM 3</i>	-31.05	20000	≥ 4000	38.62	7.57	2000	2000-2500
	<i>HTM 4</i>	-31.91	20000	≥ 4000	35.03	3.12	2000	2000*
	<i>HTM 5</i>	-32.34	20000	≥ 63	29.19	-3.15 (Peak)	2000	No boosting
	<i>HTM 6**</i>	-34.90	125	≥ 63	21.23	-13.67 (Peak)	1250	No boosting
	<i>NCM**</i>	"	"	"	"	"	"	"
C					44.65			
	<i>HTM 1</i>	-30.11	16000	≥ 5000	42.39	12.28	800	630-3150
	<i>HTM 2</i>	-30.57	20000	≥ 4000	40.07	9.50	800	630-3150
	<i>HTM 3</i>	-31.14	20000	≥ 4000	37.07	5.93	800	800-2500
	<i>HTM 4</i>	-31.34	20000	≥ 4000	34.74	3.39	800	800*
	<i>HTM 5</i>	-31.48	20000	≥ 3150	31.72	0.24	800	800*
	<i>HTM 6</i>	-31.54	20000	≥ 1000	29.04	-2.50 (Peak)	800	No boosting
	<i>NCM</i>	-32.37	8000	≥ 1000	29.61	-2.77 (Peak)	800	No boosting

*This region only occupied a single third octave band. **NCM and HTM 6 were identical for Device B.

TABLE A.3: Active spectral modification properties analysis of results shown in Fig. 4 of the paper.

Device	Mode	Attenuation			Modification Range (dB)	Boosting (Peak)		
		Amount (dB)	Freq. (Hz)	Region (Hz)		Amount (dB)	Freq. (Hz)	Region (Hz)
A					64.92			
	<i>HTM 1</i>	-6.81	200	200*	40.52	33.71	3150	≥ 1000
	<i>HTM 2</i>	-8.25	200	160-315	40.75	32.51	3150	≥ 1000
	<i>HTM 3</i>	-9.70	200	80-500	41.00	31.30	3150	≥ 1000
	<i>HTM 4</i>	-11.13	200	≤ 500	41.26	30.13	3150	≥ 1000
	<i>HTM 5</i>	-12.72	200	≤ 500	41.64	28.91	3150	≥ 1600
	<i>HTM 6</i>	-14.30	200	≤ 800	42.02	27.72	3150	≥ 1600
	<i>NCM</i>	-31.21	160	≤ 2000	43.95	12.74	3150	1250-5000
B					64.46			
	<i>HTM 1</i>	-10.47	63	≤ 100	41.00	30.53	2500	≥ 1000
	<i>HTM 2</i>	-13.40	63	≤ 800	41.02	27.61	2500	≥ 1250
	<i>HTM 3</i>	-17.08	63	≤ 800	41.09	24.00	2500	1250-10000
	<i>HTM 4</i>	-22.11	63	≤ 1000	41.28	19.17	2500	1250-10000
	<i>HTM 5</i>	-30.33	63	≤ 1000	42.05	11.72	2500	1600-4000
	<i>HTM 6**</i>	-33.94	125	≤ 1250	36.56	2.62	8000	8000*
	<i>NCM**</i>	"	"	"	"	"	"	"
C					51.49			
	<i>HTM 1</i>	-7.74	200	160-250	37.37	29.63	800	400-12500
	<i>HTM 2</i>	-9.68	63	≤ 100	36.52	26.84	800	400-10000
	<i>HTM 3</i>	-12.69	63	≤ 315	35.97	23.28	800	500-10000
	<i>HTM 4</i>	-14.35	63	≤ 315	35.08	20.74	800	630-8000
	<i>HTM 5</i>	-15.58	63	≤ 400	33.17	17.59	800	630-8000
	<i>HTM 6</i>	-16.08	63	≤ 400	30.92	14.84	800	630-3150
	<i>NCM</i>	-21.86	63	≤ 400	36.44	14.58	800	630-1250

*This region only occupied a single third octave band. **NCM and HTM 6 were identical for Device B.

Appendix B

Temporal discontinuities in device performance

FIGURE B.1: Spectrograms showing temporal discontinuities in the performance of devices A and B at a presentation level of 105 dB SPL. Discontinuities are visible approximately every 6-8 s in the left ear of Device A's HTM 1 response and from 1-5 s in the equivalent right ear response. For Device B's NCM, discontinuities are visible as vertical lines below 5 kHz throughout the duration of the recording in the left ear response and instantaneous shifts in the frequency spectrum at approximately 1-2, 5-6, and 13-19 s in the right ear response.

Appendix C

Onset of spectral modification for devices

FIGURE C.1: Spectrograms showing the onset of spectral modification of diffuse pink noise for Device A's HTM 5, Device B's HTM 1, and Device C's HTM 1. For Device A the onset is visible between 2-3 s, while the onset is instantaneous for devices B and C.